

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MODERN FINANCIAL CRISES - CAUSES, CONSEQUENCES, CONCLUSIONS

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Abstract

The increasing frequency of financial crises in recent decades has sparked research interest in elucidating their emergence, genesis, and development. In this article, we briefly review the leading views on contemporary financial crises and the causes behind them.

Keywords: crisis, finance, banking.

Financial crises are catastrophic events for any economy, as they lead to the collapse of the financial system, which in turn leads to the collapse of the real economy. As Gorton and Ordóñez note, financial crises occur in all market economies, both emerging market economies and developed economies, regardless of whether they have a central bank and whether they have introduced deposit insurance, thus the authors consider them to be an inherent characteristic of market economies and an inherent flaw in their financial markets. (Gorton, Ordóñez, 2023). As a number of other studies have shown, the frequency of crises is the same in high- and middle-income countries (Reinhart and Rogoff (2009, 2013), Kindleberger and Aliber (2005)).

The increased frequency of crises, especially in the 21st century (Global Financial Crisis of 2007, Eurozone Sovereign Debt Crisis of 2010, COVID-19 crisis), combined with the increased instability of the modern global financial system (over-indebted countries, high real estate prices, volatile capital flows) has raised concerns among financial circles (Bandt, Drumetz, Pfister, 2021). Recent financial crises have become increasingly widespread and devastating, affecting the core of the global economic system, affecting economies that generate a significant share of the world's economic output, and generating significant long-term instabilities (Yılmaz, 2021).

All these crises lead some authors (Hsu, 2017) to argue that the contemporary global financial system, which is based on the efficient markets hypothesis, i.e. that financial markets, as self-correcting and symmetric, automatically reflect all available information about assets through changes in their prices, has suffered a total failure and requires a rethinking of the economic foundations of the financial management of the economy. Even the former chairman of the US Federal Reserve, Alan Greenspan, admits that he was wrong to approach monetary policy from the ideology of the free market, since instead of reaching equilibrium, markets can stagnate without active measures from regulators.

This also necessitates rethinking the nature and systematic nature of financial crises, with some authors in recent years advocating the thesis that financial crises are transforming from a "black swan" phenomenon, i.e. as a rare and completely unpredictable, but massive

event, into a "white swan" phenomenon, i.e. considering that crises are the result of a simple, repetitive and predictable process (Yılmaz, 2021).

If we look at the impact of the Global Financial Crisis, its impact was not limited to a narrowly defined market - geographical or asset class, but rather gave rise to a global breakdown of trust between financial institutions, which very quickly affected the real economies of countries, regardless of their participation in the affected financial markets Mazzola, P. (2022). Financial globalization, deregulation, liberalization, unregulated expansion of financial markets, the introduction of new and innovative financial instruments led to the development of the so-called shadow banking and increasingly risky speculation in financial markets and the transformation of the global financial system (Marichal, 2009). This corresponds to the change in the nature of financial crises noted by Grytten and Koilo, which have transformed from those caused by banking panics and credit crashes into financial crises caused by stock market crashes, bursting financial bubbles, currency crises and defaults by countries (Grytten, Koilo, 2019).

It is worth noting here that in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, financial crises were most often caused by bank runs and bank failures. The problems in the banking sector, which at that time was dominant in the financial sector of countries, very quickly transferred to the real economy, disrupting the normal relationship between economic agents seeking and offering resources, which in turn led to a contraction of the activities of enterprises, respectively. a decrease in the volume of production and the number of people employed in them. The resulting inflation and stagnation of the economy led to a decrease in consumer demand for goods and services, as a result of reduced disposable income and a lower standard of living, which in turn further reduced industrial production as a result of reduced solvent demand (Copolovitch, Singer, 2020).

Typically, a banking panic, which can later develop into a financial crisis, is triggered by a key event that makes depositors question the ability to convert their deposits or other short-term banking and/or financial obligations into cash. During the panic, banking institutions find themselves unable to fulfill their contractual obligations, and since there are no economic agents

willing to buy part of the bank's assets in order to recapitalize the institution, the latter falls into a state of insolvency (Gordon, Tallman, 2018).

As a number of authors point out, the main reason for the insolvency of the banking institution lies in the classic banking business model in which banks attract short-term loans (deposits of depositors) and at the same time provide long-term credit resources to their borrowers, which creates a significant imbalance between the maturity structure of the bank's assets and liabilities (Bojinov, 2013a, 2013b). This imbalance is dictated both by the purely commercial interest of banking institutions to generate income, but at the same time it is also of interest to society and the economy, as it consolidates the free funds of small individual depositors, directing them to the development of the economy and business, thus transforming liquidity into a socially productive function (Moro, Beker, 2016).

When this event goes beyond the scope of the individual banking and/or financial institution and covers multiple institutions or the entire financial system, the banking panic becomes systemic, and the crisis becomes a systemic financial crisis. This process is usually realized through the so-called contagion process, in which the risk of insolvency is transferred from one bank to another, especially when these banks have interbank exposures to the distressed bank, common asset exposure or through the domino effect due to counterparty risk (Gordon, Tallman, 2018, Moro, Beker, 2016).

It is worth noting here that in recent financial crises, especially the Global Financial Crisis of 2007, banks played a much more modest role in their emergence and development. For example, at the root of the 2007 crisis, it was precisely the problems with short-term financial debt instruments that gave rise to the financial panic, and as Ben Bernanke pointed out in his testimony before the Commission to Inquire into the Financial Crisis in the United States (2011), twelve of the thirteen most important financial institutions in the United States were on the verge of failure within a week or two after the bankruptcy of Lehman Brothers (Gordon, Tallman, 2018).

As Moro and Becker (2016) point out, the 2007–2009 US financial crisis was not a classic banking crisis, but a securities-based financial crisis, triggered by the enormous development of securities and derivatives. They emphasize that the modern securities-based financial system has significant advantages, related both to the possibility of almost unlimited geographical expansion of issuers, significantly expanding the potential market for their securities, and to the existence of a secondary market, allowing investors to trade their securities before their maturity. In this way, the modern financial system, by analogy with the banking institution, allows, through the securities market, to aggregate various investors with diversifiable short-term liquidity needs in order to provide long-term resources (debt and equity in the form of bonds and shares) for production purposes, while trading on the secondary market provides a significantly higher degree of operability and mobility of the attracted and invested financial re-

sources, and through the use of various derivative financial instruments, the possibilities for hedging and risk-taking for all participants have increased (Moro, Beker, 2016).

Insofar as practically all financial intermediaries, banks and non-bank institutions hold securities of varying degrees of liquidity on their balance sheets, they are also exposed to the risk of changes in the prices of these securities on the financial markets. The financial crisis caused by the securities market has exactly the same economic logic as the banking panic: investors' concern about the prices of the securities they hold can make them want to transform them into more liquid assets in the form of other securities or cash. The excessive supply of securities, in turn, causes a decline in their prices and the issuer or trader's refusal to buy them at a given price or at par. In turn, this refusal further depresses the prices of securities and, by analogy with financial contagion, is capable of negatively affecting a similar class of securities, even though their issuers do not have liquidity problems. As Giovannini (2010) points out, the securities market fails to function and provide liquidity services both when market participants themselves are unable to value the securities being traded and when participants lose confidence in the ability of other market participants to settle their obligations in the market (Giovannini, 2010).

As Shenai (2018) points out, shadow banking is based on transactions in two main types of securities: asset-backed commercial paper (ABCP) and repurchase agreements (“repos”), which are a kind of short-term “deposits” in the shadow banking system. In turn, shadow banks use the proceeds from ABCP and repos to purchase long-term securitized assets: asset-backed securities (ABS), or bonds backed by cash flows from pooled loans from sectors such as housing, credit card and auto loans, and other types of underlying collateral, thus making the security counterparties in the ABS loan portfolios a kind of “borrowers” (see Fig. 1.2) (Shenai, 2018).

As Gorton (2010) points out, unlike traditional regulated banks, shadow banks are significantly more exposed to the risk of runs, as they do not have government guarantees for the funds and securities invested in them (Gorton, 2010). The economic boom in the US since the early 2000s, combined with rising housing prices, further boosted the development of shadow banking, as their transactions mainly through ABCP, repos and securitization created systemic vulnerability in the system to falling housing prices, which was manifested in a full-scale flight of investors from the shadow banking system, especially after the bankruptcy of the investment bank Lehman Brothers (Shenai, 2018).

And if we can argue that the root of the Global Financial Crisis is imperfections and distortions in the financial markets, then the sources of the recession after the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic are mainly due to the administrative measures taken to limit the spread of the disease, which also reflected on the normal implementation of business activities in the economy. The termination of a significant part of production and services requiring the physical presence of people

led to a kind of "freezing of the economy", a decline and change in the profile of consumer demand, as well as disruption of global supply chains (International Monetary Fund, 2020). All this led to a drastic reduction in cash flows to both consumers and companies, reflecting on a significant increase in the risk of non-service of granted corporate and consumer loans, which in turn increased the risks of problems in banking institutions and the financial sector as a whole. The lockdowns imposed on the global economy led to a depreciation of assets on capital markets and a sharp increase in the risks associated with them, causing subsequent liquidity problems and a contraction in the granting of new loans by banks. And although governments adopted and implemented significant anti-crisis support measures for the entire economy, including the financial sector, the shock to the global economy triggered a supply-driven recession, combined with accelerating inflation, an energy crisis and disruption of supply chains.

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